

STUDIES IN THE BEHAVIOUR OF BI-UNIVALENT SALTS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART IV. CADMIUM NITRATE

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From the E.M.F. measurement of the cell

cadmium nitrate appears to be completely dissociated up to a concentration of 0.1M. Transport measurements as well as cryoscopic data lend support to the above conclusions.

Righellato and Davies (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 592) studied the conductance of cadmium nitrate and determined the dissociation constant of

on the assumption that the first stage of dissociation

is complete and that intermediate ion CdNO_3^+ has an ionic conductance of 40.

Potentiometric investigations were undertaken with the hope that they will throw some light on the nature of cadmium nitrate. The cell of the type :

was studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cadmium amalgam containing 12% of cadmium, prepared by dissolving Analar cadmium metal in mercury, distilled under vacuum, was used.

The cadmium nitrate solution was made by dissolving Analar cadmium nitrate in double distilled water. Its exact concentration was determined by analysis. The estimation was done by using oxine as a precipitant and adding excess of bromate, followed by potassium iodide and then titrating with thiosulphate (Vogel, "Quantitative Analysis", p. 455). The stock solution was kept in a closely sealed Jena bottle. From time to time its strength was checked. The other solutions were prepared from the stock solution.

The cell vessels and the bridge were of the type used previously (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 683). Each experiment was done in duplicate and the duplicates agreed within 0.2 m.v. For performing the duplicate experiments four half elements were required, two of which had the solution of the same concentration. The half cells having the same composition were always checked against each other. They seldom differed by more than 0.1 m.v. and if they did, they were rejected. Two half elements of different concentrations, checked as described above, were joined through a salt bridge and readings taken. All the measurements were done at 30°.

TABLE I

Concentrations. (g. mol./litre).	Cd _x Hg _y Cd(NO ₃) ₂ Bridge Cd(NO ₃) ₂ Cd _x Hg _y		Recorded E.M.F.	Corrected E.M.F.	Calc. E.M.F.	Diff.
	c ₁	c ₂				
0.1 — 0.01	10 M 5		0.02140 0.02165 }	0.02152 volt	0.012164 volt	0.12 m.v.
0.1 — 0.02	10 5		0.0142 0.0145 }	0.0143	0.014976	0.67
0.1 — 0.04	10 5		0.00845 0.0087 }	0.0086	0.008407	0.19
0.1 — 0.06	10 5		0.00450 0.00460 }	0.00455	0.004905	0.25
0.1 — 0.08	10 5		0.0020 0.0019 }	0.00195	0.00113	0.8
0.08 — 0.01	10 5		0.01910 0.01940 }	0.01925	0.01953	0.3
0.08 — 0.02	10 5		0.0141 0.0142 }	0.01415	0.0139	0.2
0.08 — 0.04	10 5		0.0064 0.0067 }	0.00655	0.0063	0.25
0.08 — 0.06	10 5		0.0024 0.0025 }	0.00245	0.00208	0.37
0.08 — 0.01	10 5		0.01720 0.01730 }	0.01725	0.01665	0.6
0.08 — 0.02	10 5		0.0106 0.0107 }	0.01065	0.01027	0.38
0.08 — 0.04	10 5		0.00340 0.00355 }	0.0035	0.00365	0.35
0.04 — 0.01	10 5		0.0118 0.0119 }	0.01185	0.01279	0.94
0.04 — 0.02	10 5		0.0065 0.0067 }	0.00665	0.0064	0.25

The results are shown in Table I. Column 1 gives the concentrations of the two solutions of cadmium nitrate in g. mol./litre. Column 2 gives the concentration of ammonium nitrate used as the bridge solution in g. mol./litre. Column 3 gives the recorded E.M.F. Column 4 gives the E.M.F. corrected for liquid junction by Bjerrums method (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, 53, 428). This corrected E.M.F. should be given by

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{f_1 C_1}{f_2 C_2}$$

The activity coefficient 'f' of cadmium ion could not be calculated from the mean activity coefficient of cadmium nitrate, as has been done for lead ion in our previous work (*loc. cit.*) as no reliable data for the mean activity coefficient of cadmium nitrate exist. The activity coefficient of cadmium ion has been assumed to be equal to that of barium ion at the same ionic strength, on the basis that same valence type ion has the same activity coefficient in a solution of the same ionic strength. The activity coefficient of barium ion has been calculated from the mean activity coefficient of barium nitrate, potassium nitrate and potassium chloride. Now, having known the activity coefficient, 'E' has been calculated and the values of E.M.F. thus obtained are given in column 5. They agree fairly well with the corrected values given in column 4. The differences are given in column 6, which shows that the difference between the observed and the calculated E.M.F. is never more than 1 m.v. So it may be taken that at least over the range of concentrations studied here, cadmium nitrate is completely dissociated.

This view is supported by the cryoscopic data (Landolt, Börnstein, Roth, Scheel, Table 1923, p. 1439) given below, which do not show any appreciable change in molecular depression up to a 0.1691 molal solution.

g. mole 1000 g. of water	0.01997	0.4873	0.1691	1.016
Mol. depression	5.18	5.15	5.12	6.45

It gets further support from the study of transference number of cadmium ion in cadmium nitrate solution. The apparatus shown in Fig. 1 was used in the experiment to meet our need. In some experiments both silver and iodine coulometers (Fig. 2) were used and in some, only one was used. The solution in the silver coulometer was always filtered through a glass sintered crucible to collect any silver which might not be adhering to the coulometer.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Only the anode solution of the iodine coulometer was analysed. The transport number of the cadmium was calculated from the formula,

$$t^+ = 1 - \frac{\text{Increase in the number of g. equiv. of Cd in anode compartment}}{\text{g. equiv. of silver deposited or iodine liberated}}$$

when the anode solution was analysed. When the cathode solution was analysed, the formula used was

$$t^+ = 1 - \frac{\text{Decrease in the number of g. equiv. of Cd in cathode compartment}}{\text{g. equiv. of silver deposited or iodine liberated}}$$

The estimation of cadmium was done as explained earlier in this paper. The middle compartment was analysed in the case of 0.0964, 0.1839, 0.485 and 0.8491 *M* solutions and no change was recorded in the composition. The results of the experiments are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Conc. of cadmium nitrate.	Coulometer.	Compartment analysed.	Number of determinations made.	Maximum & minimum values of transference number.	Mean value of t^+ .
0.01 <i>M</i>	Iodine as well as silver	Anode	3	0.4673-0.4398	0.453
0.02		"	3	0.4529-0.4311	0.443
0.05		"	5	0.4392-0.4143	0.426
0.10	"	Cathode and anode, both.	7	0.4373-0.406	0.420
0.20	"	Anode	4	0.4432-0.4128	0.435
0.35	"	Cathode and anode both.	3	0.3904-0.3631	0.380
0.50	"	"	5	0.3200-0.3600	0.335
1.00	"	"	5	0.2611-0.2955	0.280
1.00	"	Anode	3	0.2038-0.1816	0.196

Calc. transport number from $\frac{t^+(\frac{1}{2}\text{Cd}^{++})}{t^+(\frac{1}{2}\text{Cd}^{++}) + t^-(\text{NO}_3^-)}$ is 0.43.

The following observations were made during the transport number experiments:

- (1) Some cadmium nitrite is invariably formed in the anode compartment. The formation of this nitrite is independent of the current density at the anode, as even a change of current density by about hundred times has no appreciable effect on the amount of nitrite formed. The ratio of the gram equivalents of the nitrite formed to the gram equivalents of the silver deposited in the coulometer steadily increases with concentration.

Conc.	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.35	0.50
Ratio	0.33	0.35	0.36	0.38	0.40	0.41

- (2) At concentrations up to 0.2*M* a spongy deposit of cadmium is formed on the mercury at the cathode. A small amount of nitrite is also formed simultaneously. When the concentration becomes higher, neither the spongy deposit of cadmium nor nitrite is formed in the cathode compartment.
- (3) No nitrite was formed in the middle compartment in any case.
- (4) A white deposit was formed at the anode. The amount of the deposit increases with increase in current density and increase of concentration of cadmium nitrate. This deposit is appreciable at concentrations greater than 0.5*M*. This deposit when dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid oxidises potassium iodide to iodine, and when dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid, reduces permanganate. It does not give perchromic acid test. As the liberation of iodine or reduction of permanganate is only small in amount, it may be due to adsorbed nitrite.
- (5) It became necessary to see if the transport number calculated from the analysis of the anode compartment was vitiated by the formation of the white deposit. So some cathode solutions in which nitrite was not formed were used for the calculation of the transport number and it was found that the same results were obtained.
- (6) Some finely powdered cadmium was added to cadmium nitrate solution and it was found that appreciable amount of nitrite as well as a white deposit was formed and this amount increased with the concentration of cadmium nitrate.

The white deposit may be due to action of NO_3^- on metallic cadmium. This is also given by KNO_3 as noted by a number of workers. (Mellor, "Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry"). If the nitrite formation is due to the reaction between NO_3^- and metallic cadmium, then the transference number will not be appreciably affected by the formation of the white deposit. Since the transference number is not affected in our experiment due to the white deposit, we may conclude that the white deposit is formed as a result of the interaction of metallic cadmium and nitrate ion.